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Divine Mandate in Genesis 1:27 and LGBTQPLUS: Roles of Pastoral Counsellors

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Abstract

The world is going through rapid and drastic changes that question almost everything that has to do with security, morality, religion, education, economics, and the daily living of people everywhere. The changes are also questioning the origin of the world, the existence of God, and his standard for human existence. One of the changes that are spreading through the globe with human justification and, in some places, legal approval is LGBTQPLUS. Different methods are being employed to give orientation on this new way of life and to influence people, especially children and youth to imbibe and practice it. And this practice questions the injunction found in Genesis 1:27. Pastoral counsellors are individuals who are trained and equipped to guide people in living right according to the dictates of God. What are the roles of pastoral counsellors in this global phenomenon? The study is anchored on James Marcia's status theory. Adopting the phenomenology design of qualitative research, the study employed interviews using focus groups to collect data from 16 pastors with different pastoral experiences. The collected data were analysed thematically. The findings indicated that LGBTQPLUS is a way of attacking the divine mandate in Gen. 1:27 that God created humans male and female and in essence establishing atheistic philosophy. The study concluded with the recommendations that pastoral counsellors should engage people in understanding the phenomenon and guide them in living according to God's injunction.

Keywords: God's injunction, Human Existence, LGBTQPLUS, Morality and Religion, Pastoral Counsellors

Introduction

The world is going through a period when sexuality has become anything that anyone may think it is. Each person has the right to determine their sexuality differently from what is given from the creation of the world according to Genesis 1:27 which says, "So God created mankind in his own image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them" (NIV). This Bible passage is explicit that it is difficult for it to be misunderstood. With the passing of time and the entrance of sin, there came a muddling of sexuality from being male and female as created by God. This is indicated by God instructing the Israelites saying "Do not have sexual relations with a man as one does with a woman; that is detestable" (Leviticus 18:22, NIV). There is a further deterioration in the understanding and practices of sexuality among humans in this current dispensation beyond the command God gave in Leviticus. The known sexuality in the world now is **LGBTQPLUS** which is an acronym for Lesbian, Gay, bisexual, transgender, intersex, queer/questioning, asexual, and many other terms (such as non-binary and pansexual). Many have used the Bible to justify the new sexuality or sexual orientation. Markham (2023), justified that the Bible is in support of the new sexual orientation because it was unlikely that the biblical authors had any notion of sexual orientation in their time. A whole study has been carried out in Nigeria on sexual orientation which advocated for the acceptance of

LGBTQPLUS (Alimi, Boynton, Struharova & Wood, 2017). The study indicated that people of age groups 18–24 (36%) and 25–34 (51%) hold to and practice this new sexual orientation. The study is based on the personality identity theory by James Marcia.

The study reviewed relevant literature to bring about the understanding of some concepts. One of the important issues in the study is personality identity. The concept of sexuality identity is within the general understanding of personality identity. Identity according to Oyserman, Elmore, and Smith (2012), can be traits and characteristics, social relations, gender roles, and social group memberships that define who someone is. This can be focused on the past, present or future. Sometimes, what people have identified can change with time based on more understanding, exposure, or other factors. Personality identity, therefore, is what an individual perceives to be the characteristics, social relations or self-understanding possessed by the person. It is the answer a person gives to the question “who are you?” (Vignoles, 2017, p. 1). Sometimes, people can wish they are something different from what/who they are, and when a situation becomes favourable, the desired identity may be achieved. Identity is a personal orientation that provides meaning-making lens and focuses someone’s attention on some features of the immediate context. It is a personal awareness of one’s existence in the immediate context. Therefore, personality identity is what a person understands him/herself to be in the immediate context of existence.

James Marcia in his identity theory, presented “four stage progression through which individuals may achieve a strong sense of identity” (Kim, 2010, p. 107). Although he did not ascribe specific age group to each stage of identity but it is clear when someone may decide to switch identity. The identity stages according to James are adapted and summarized in the following table.

Table One: Identity Statuses (adapted from Kim, 2010)

Identity Status	Description	Crisis Level	Commitments to Ideal
Diffusion	Avoidance of responsibility; impulsive; low self-esteem; avoids commitments to parents, school, and work	Low because of avoidance of responsibility	Weak; subject to impulse, current situation, and positive/negative feedback
Foreclosure	Adopts the values and goals of others such as parents or significant other; very assured due to affiliation with others; authoritarian and sense of superiority over others	Low due to attaching identity to that of others, especially parents or guardians	Strong; having adopted and affirmed the commitments already made by their parents
Moratorium	Begins to have thoughts of uncertainty; rejection or weakening of parental commitments; begins to exhibit short-term commitments to	Moderate; begin to ask identity-related questions to self	Weak; the previous answers from parents no longer respond to all of their life questions

	relationships, school, task			
Achievement	Make their commitments on their terms; determines their values, establishes commitments and relationships, and assumes responsibility for decision making	High due to complete engagement with identity crisis; resolved it by assuming responsibility for making choices (with multiple alternatives)	Strong; committed individual choice	has by

The diffusion stage indicates a critical stage that serves as the foundation for whatever identity someone will adopt in later years despite the avoidance of responsibility and other characteristics. It is on this stage that foreclosure is built upon when parental and significant others' values and goals are adopted. This stage is important because, even in the stage of moratorium when a person looks inward to determine identity, whatever has been imbibed during the first two stages can determine how a person will navigate through moratorium stage. Moratorium stage marks the period when things may go right or wrong afterward when the person reaches achievement stage. At the achievement stage, a person is ready to fight for whatever is already determined or established as a personal identity, especially in sexual identity which is the focus of this study.

Sexual-identity

Sexual orientation according to Hall (2019) is a multidimensional phenomenon that involves someone's sexual attraction, sexual behaviour, and sexual orientation identity. It is how a person is positioned in the three dimensions of sexuality—sexual attraction, sexual behaviour, and sexual orientation identity. These patterns according to him may be consistent or fluctuate over time. Hall (2019), acknowledged that the predominant sexual orientation and behaviour is heterosexual, but that there are other sexual expressions. It is important that Hall stated that sexuality is part of human development, which indicates that just as there can be developmental errors in development in any aspect of human life, there can also be sexual development leading to different orientations. This can be as a result of changes in hormone levels and anatomical characteristics that people personally pursue by personal choice (Teich, 2012). Sexuality orientation is closely associated with gender identity and expression. Identity has to do with the internal sense of being a man, woman, or another gender, while gender expression is how a person demonstrates their gender (clothing, hairstyle, speech, behaviour, and appearance). Despite all these, Hall (2019), recognised the dual sexual identity he called "assigned at birth" which is either male or female. The following table summarises the different sexuality orientations that resulted from factors—hormonal changes, social influence, personal choices, etc.

Intersex	A variety of biophysical manifestation where a person's genome or sexual anatomy do not fit the typical definitions of male or female
Transsexual	A subset of transgender people who pursue medical interventions to change their sex characteristics so that they match their gender identity
Gender	

Identity

Cisgender A person whose birth sex aligns with their gender identity (e.g. male and man, or female and woman)

Transgender A person whose sex assigned at birth does not align with their gender identity; many gender identities fall under the umbrella term of transgender

Genderqueer A person who has multiple genders (man and woman, bigender, and pangender), no gender (e. g. agender and gender free), or movement between genders (e. g. genderfluid)

Man A person whose gender identity is connected to maleness and/or masculinity

Woman A person whose gender identity is connected to femaleness and/or femininity

Sexual

Orientation

Identity

Heterosexual A person who is sexually attracted to people of the opposite sex or gender

Gay A person who is sexually attracted to people of the same sex or gender

Lesbian A female/woman who is sexually attracted to other female/woman

Bisexual A person who is sexually attracted to males and females

Polysexual A person who is sexually attracted to people of multiple sexes or genders

Pansexual or A person who is sexually attracted to people of all sexes or genders

Omnisexual

Asexual A person with a lack or low level of sexual attraction to anyone

Questioning A person who is uncertain who they are sexually attracted to

Queer An umbrella term for people of diverse sexualities who are not heterosexual; an alternative identity to the traditional non-heterosexual identities such as gay, lesbian, or bisexual

Androsexual A person who is sexually attracted to males, men, and/or masculine people

Gynesexual A person who is sexually attracted to females, women, and/or feminine people

Skoliosexual A person who is sexually attracted to people who are transgender or genderqueer

In a study conducted by National Survey of Family and Growth from 2011 –2013 according to Hall (2019) involving people of ages 18 to 44, it was indicated that 81% of the women in the study were attracted to only opposite sex, 92.1% of the men were attracted to only opposite sex. This implies that as of 2013, most of the people were still attracted to only opposite sex. When it comes to sexual behaviour, 95.3% of women and 93.5% of men had engaged in only opposite-sex sexual behaviour while 17.4% of women and 6.2% of men had engaged in same-sex sexual behaviour. In addition, 92.3% of women 95.1% of men identified themselves as heterosexual.

Hall (2019), stated that the etymology of heterosexuality is almost never questioned because it is the only way of ensuring survival of human species. Irrespective of many other orientations, the one that has always been is the one that can fulfil the purpose of continuity of life. Some of the factors responsible for different kind of sexuality orientations include, genetic, hormonal, and environmental (Cook, 2020).

LGBTQPLUS

LGBTQPLUS stands for different kinds of sexual orientations being practices by people. This has been legalized in some nations like the United States, United Kingdom and Canada. The orientation and practices have not been publicly accepted in Africa and specifically in Nigeria. There are different write-ups on LGBTQPLUS and different more publication emerge each day with the name increasing in letters as a result of introduction of new orientation and practices each day. Nigeria is perceived as one of the most anti-gay nations in Africa and in the world. The laws in Nigeria (Same Sex Marriage Prohibition Acts of 2014) criminalised any sexual act different from heterosexual behaviour (Chimakonam & Agada, 2020). Some studies have been done on the issue of LGBTQPLUS in Nigeria (Alimi, 2017; Martins, 2022; Ogueji & Ogueji, 2022). Despite the promotions and quiet efforts to institutionalize it in Nigeria, it is still observed by scholars that the practices of LGBTQ will be difficult to have a widespread in Nigeria due to religion and culture (Martins, 2022).

In order to safeguard young people from this phenomenon, Martins (2022) suggested that the curriculum of primary and secondary schools and tertiary institutions be modified to include multiple sexual orientation in order to create awareness among students and enlighten them on the issues of LGBTQ. He also recommended that religious institutions should constantly preach against LGBTQ among their followers while traditional rulers should preach against it to safeguard Nigerian cultures.

Genesis 1:27

Before God instructed the Israelites not to “have sexual relationship with a man as one does with a woman” (Leviticus 18:22, NIV), there is an indication that such practices have been taking place in some nations, especially in Assyria and Egypt from where God brought them out (Thomas, 2006). In the beginning, at creation the Bible indicates what God created when it comes to sexual orientation as it is written in Genesis 1:27, “So God created mankind in his own image, in the image of God he created them; **male and female** he created them” (NIV). Scholars have explored this passage considering the original language which was Hebrew and they have given an insight into understanding the passage. The Hebrew word for male is *Zakar* (adjective, singular and absolute). This denotes the sex that can fertilize or inseminate female to produce offspring. The Hebrew word for female is *Neqebah* (adjective, feminine, singular and absolute). The word denotes the sex that can bear offspring or produce eggs (Soanes & Stevenson, 2011). These expressions clearly indicate the purpose of the existence of two the types of gender.

The creation of two different sexes by God presupposes his intention for them to “Be fruitful and increase in number, fill the earth and subdue it” (Genesis 1:28, NIV). It was in the creation of humans that the pronouncement “male and female he created them” to differentiate the gift of fertility from God to humans from that of other living creature who may not necessarily be aware of their existence as humans were given. Humans are to meet the requirement of the gift—fertility. It is only in human that the duality of sex finds its

expression in the instruction of holy wedlock which is also called conjugal bond (Calvin, 1981; Nichol, 1953). It was God who identified that “It is not good for a man to be alone” (Genesis 2:18, NIV) and he was the one that gave the woman (female) to add to the man (male) to be one (complete). The pair was man (male) and woman (female) and there was no other sex or gender (Calvin, 1981). And everything created by God from the beginning was “very good” (Genesis 1:31) including the “male and female.”

Nelson (2019), argued that no human is born differently from being either male or female. He made it clear that from scientific point of view there has not been evidence that people are born or could be born differently from being male or female. The current multiple sexual orientation is a complete deviation from biblical evidence in the creation account. Nelson gave some factors that may be considered as responsible for the multiple sexual orientation which are, a disrupted family life in early years, lack of unconditional love on the part of either parent, envy of the same or the opposite sex or a life controlled by various fears and feelings of isolation, incest or molestation, dominant mothers and weak fathers, and demonic oppression. From Nelson’s view, it could be said that dysfunctional home and early un-monitored relationship among children could be responsible for multiple sexual orientations and practices as they are in the 21st century.

Another biblical passage that brings some clarity to multiple orientation is Romans 1:18–32, specifically verses 24, 25–27 which reads,

There God gave them over in the sinful desires of their hearts to sexual impurity for the degrading of their bodies with one another.... their women exchange natural sexual relations for unnatural ones. In the same way the men also abandoned natural relations with women and were inflamed with lust for one another. Men committed shameful acts with other men, and received in themselves the due penalty for their error (NIV).

The above is a result of suppressing the truth about the knowledge of God as stated in verse 18–21. “For although they knew God, they neither glorified him as God nor gave thanks to him, but their thinking became futile and their foolish hearts were darkened” (Romans 1:21, NIV). From the passage it could be said that the multiple sexual orientation which is adding more nomenclature, is a result of suppressing the truth of God. It could be juxtaposed that the truth is accepting God as the Creator because it is his creative act that led to the creation of humans who he made male and female which has been changed from being that to LGBTQPLUS.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims at analysing Gen. 1:27 and relate it to the current sexual orientation (LGBTQPLUS) being promoted globally and to find out the role pastoral counsellors are to play in the phenomenon. The objectives are to:

1. Examine the validity of the divine injunction in Gen. 1:27
2. Understand the goal of the LGBTQPLUS as a sexual orientation
3. Explore the role of pastoral counsellors in the phenomenon

Research Questions

1. Does the injunction of “male and female he created them” still stand?
2. What is the goal of the LGBTQPLUS as a sexual orientation?
3. What are the roles of pastoral counsellors in this situation?

Methodology

This study adopted qualitative approach with interview as the means of data collection. Since the focus of the study was on the roles of pastoral counsellors, the study used a focus group discussion. The group was made up of 16 pastors with one female pastor among them. The ages of the participants ranged from 26 years to 50 years, with diverse pastoral experiences. The group was met in a classroom where they received lectures. Permission was taken to conduct the interview which was granted by the entire group members. A background to study was given for proper understanding of the subject of study and for full attention and participation from the group members.

The participants responded to the following questions: What is your understanding of Genesis 1:27 in term of sexual orientation? What is your view of emerging sexual orientation (LGBTQPLUS)? How well established in Nigeria is the sexual orientation? What should be the roles of pastoral counsellors in the situation? What could be the factors responsible for such sexual orientations and practices? Could such practices have any effect on people's life? Could such have effect on the knowledge of God? What could be the implication on the knowledge of the Bible? What should be roles of pastoral counsellors in such situation? Responses were recorded using pen and paper. The data were analysed thematically. The collected data were analysed thematically and four themes emerged from the analysis.

Findings

Knowledge of LGBTQPLUS: Most of the respondents indicated their awareness of LGBTQPLUS but not all have deep knowledge of it. To those who have the knowledge, it is a community of people who are fighting for the freedom of multiple sexual orientation and practices. According to one of the respondents, it is a "deviation from biblical perspective of human sexuality." According to the group, LGBTQPLUS is a movement that is infiltrating every human society and endeavour. It has no respect for religion or anything of value. In Nigeria, according to the group, only few bishops are speaking against the orientation and practice because it has established itself even in Christian church. "Some pastors or men of God" according to a member of the group, "have promoted the orientation and engaged in the practices."

Effect of LGBTQPLUS: When it comes to the effect of LGBTQPLUS, the group argued that it is a movement that is bringing confusion about the knowledge of God, and is against God. The group specifically mentioned that it is a movement that works to contradict the creative work of God and especially Genesis 1:27 where it is written that "God created them male and female." In essence according to the group, LGBTQPLUS is to promote the removal of the law of God; "a strategy to further alienate humans from God and establish emptiness in humans." Looking at the movement critically, according to the group, it could be said that the goal is to attack the Bible, presenting it as outdated, irrelevant, and eventually to lead to a religion yet to be seen which will be a religion without God, moral, and holiness.

Factors responsible for the new sexual orientation: The group discussed some possible factors that could bring about such view as LGBTQPLUS. Some of such factors are, parenting negligence, lack of adequate help for teenagers to navigate a period of life when they become aware of their sexuality and orientation. The group also mentioned the desire for sexual relationships without commitment as a factor that can make someone to accept LGBTQPLUS. Given examples of such relationships, someone in the group narrated an

experience of a group of men who molested another young man because they did not want to impregnate a lady. Brainwashing was mentioned as a factor that can also make young people enter into this orientation and practices without knowing.

Role of pastoral counsellors: Although, many pastors are not aware or do not understand LGBTQPLUS and how deep it has entered into human's society, according to the group, there are still some things that pastoral counsellors can do to save people from the "pandemic." Educating of members is one of the roles of the pastoral counsellors. Pastors are to understand what the movement is and its objective, and they should educate their members from falling into it. A member of the group suggested that it is important for pastors to be educated before they can educate members and that this is needed because many pastors are not knowledgeable in LGBTQPLUS phenomenon. Pastors, in essence are playing safe when in actuality many members have quietly and innocently imbibed multiple sexual orientations and practices. The group talked about working with children to understand and avoid the orientation and practices, not only in church and homes but also in schools because of "systematic desensitisation" which occurs through school curricula, test books, cartoon and different other programs on television and majorly on the Internet.

Discussion of Findings

The findings indicated that sexuality is part of human development which is according to Hall (2019) can be abused. As part of developmental process, there is a period in life when anatomy of people goes through changes (Teich, 2012), that lead to making choices which could be detrimental to not only sexuality of individual but also to other areas of the person's life if there is no proper guide. This makes the issue of adequate parenting, according to the findings, to be an essential factor to be considered as children grow up, to help them navigate through the critical or diffusion age period (Kim, 2010) in life when choices are made. The idea of educating young people, bring about the importance of the roles of parents and pastors. Proper education at the proper age period can make someone develop appropriate orientation about sexuality and life generally. Proper education is also needed to safeguard people from systematic desensitisation. Since the multiple sexual orientation is considered to be anti-Bible, anti-God, and something that can lead to a religion without God, moral and value, and that LGBTQPLUS is a deviation from God's original creation, pastoral counsellors should teach and preach about it in their congregations and talk about it in the society.

Conclusion

LGBTQPLUS, is a movement or a community of people fighting against laws that prohibit the acceptance of multiple sexual orientation and practices. The movement is real, although, without aggression or noise, it is already entrenched deep in the Nigerian society, not only among young people, but also among adults, pastors, teachers, rich and poor people, etc. It is a movement that leads people away from the knowledge of God and works to eliminate values in the society. The practice of multiple sexual orientation leads people to live a life without commitment to one another. Specifically, it goes contrary to God's original creation of male and female and the purpose (procreation) for it, thereby insinuating creation without God. Pastoral counsellors are to equip themselves to take proper position in making

people to understand and maintain the dual sexual orientation—male and female— as created by God.

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